

SCALE FOR HANDWRITING EVALUATION (SHE)

Jella Vishnu Durga Prasad, Shwetambari Morghade, Mohammed Irshad Qureshi, Rakesh
Krishna Kovala

This tool is developed to assess handwriting in children. This tool can have significant contribution specifically to improve handwriting in normal school going children and also in children who are having issues with MOTOR EXECUTION.

Content validity of this scale has been in the process of completion.

SHE tool has total 10 tasks. Each task is evaluated on a four point likert scale, with minimum 0 and maximum 3 for each task.

This tool can be used by school teachers, health care professionals, calligraphers. No training is required to use the tool. It will take 15 minutes to complete the tool

Dominance -	Age -
Eye sight (Normal /Impaired): Nearsightedness/ Farsightedness	
Power -	
Domain 1: Body Posture	
Q: Which position does the child prefers for writing?	
Items	✓ the appropriate option
0 - Sitting and taking support of desk	
1 - Prefers Unsupported Sitting	
2 - Prefers Prone	
3 - Prefers Supported sitting	
Domain 2: Instrument hold	
Q: How the subject is holding instrument?	
Items	✓ the appropriate option
0 - Dynamic quadrupod grip	
1 - Lateral quadrupod grip	
2 - Lateral tripod grip	
3 - Dynamic tripod	
Domain 3: Angle of notebook/Paper	
Q: How the paper/book position is while writing?	

Items	✓ the appropriate option
0 - Horizontal position	
1 - Vertical position without base	
2 - Vertical position 90 degrees	
3 - 45 degrees of paper/book	

Domain 4: Handwriting angle

Q: Whether there is any inclination in handwriting?

Items	✓ the appropriate option
0 - Irregular angles	
1 - Completely sloped handwriting	
2 - Slanted degree alphabets	
3 - 90 degree alphabets	

Domain 5: Alphabets size

Q: Is there any unequal alphabets size in sentences?

Item	✓ the appropriate option
0 - All Alphabets are irregular	
1 - Alphabets are irregular sometimes	
2 - Child is maintaining equal sizes most of the time	
3 - Child is giving equal size to every alphabet	

Domain 6: Pressure on paper

Q: Does the subject keep pressure on paper?

Items	✓ the appropriate options
0 - Imprints and debosing of letters on a sheet	
1 - Imprints for three to five sheets	
2 - Imprints for one to two sheets	
3 - No imprints on the sheets	

Domain 7: Spacing between alphabets

Q: Does the child is maintaining contact spacing between alphabets?

Items	✓ the appropriate options
0 - Combines alphabets	

1 - Combines alphabets of different words	
2 - Irregular spacing sometimes near and sometimes far	
3 - Gives equal space between alphabets	

Domain 8: Spacing between words

Q: How is the spacing between words?

Items	✓ the appropriate options
0 - Unequal spacing between words	
1 - More than two finger width spacing	
2 - Two finger width spacing	
3 - Finger spacing	

Domain 9: Maintaining Consistency of alphabets

Q: Is the Child writing / drawing different alphabets every other time in sentence?

Items	✓ the appropriate options
0 – All the time	
1 – Frequently	
2 – Seldom	
3 – Never	

Domain 10: Symmetry of sentences

Q: Is there a change in alignment while composing sentences?

Items	✓ the appropriate options
0 - Irregular (not in straight line)	
1 - Wavy form sentences	
2 - Right upwards	
3 - No change in alignment	

Questions	Score			
1. Body Posture	0	1	2	3
2. Instrument hold	0	1	2	3
3. Angle of notebook/Paper	0	1	2	3
4. Handwriting angle	0	1	2	3
5. Alphabets size	0	1	2	3
6. Pressure on paper	0	1	2	3

7. Spacing between alphabets	0	1	2	3
8. Spacing between words	0	1	2	3
9. Maintaining Consistency of alphabets	0	1	2	3
10. Symmetry of sentences	0	1	2	3

TOTAL SCORE –

Scoring criteria

Maximum score – 30

Minimum score – 0